

RAPIDIO USAGE IN A BIG DATA ENVIRONMENT

September 2015

Author:
Jorge Costa

Supervisor(s):
Olof Barring

CERN openlab Summer Student Report 2015

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

RapidIO (<http://rapidio.org/>) technology is a package-switched high-performance fabric, which has been under active development since 1997. The technology is used in all 4G/LTE basestations worldwide. RapidIO is often used in embedded systems that require high reliability, low latency and deterministic operations but there may now be an opportunity to take the same value proposition to more mainstream data processing, which is the underlying motivation for this Project. The objective for the Openlab collaboration with IDT is to test and evaluate the suitability of IDT's low-latency RapidIO interconnect technology for a number of use-cases ranging from LHC Data Acquisition and Triggering to Data analytics for the data center monitoring and operations.

Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION.....	4
1.1	Motivation.....	5
1.2	Objectives	5
1.3	Document structure.....	6
2	CLUSTER AND DEVELOPMENT OVERVIEW	7
2.1	Hardware and OS Description	7
2.2	Development Library Overview.....	8
2.2.1	Channelized Messages	8
2.2.2	Shared Memory	8
3	SOFTWARE OVERVIEW.....	9
3.1	General Architecture	9
3.2	Application Level Protocol.....	10
3.3	Components And API Description	11
3.3.1	Messaging Communicator	11
3.3.2	Shared Memory Manager	12
3.3.3	File Transfer.....	13
3.4	Functionalities and Use cases	14
4	VALIDATION.....	15
4.1	Experimental Subjects	15
4.2	Experimental Setup.....	15
4.3	Experimental Results	15
5	CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK	17
5.1	Future Work	17

1 INTRODUCTION

The work reported in this document is part of a project that aims to use RapidIO to solve real problems being faced at CERN. RapidIO is a packed switched interconnect being under active development since 1997. It is an open interconnect backed by several large big companies.

Figure 1 RapidIO main goals

Figure 1 presents the main goals that RapidIO aims to achieve. RapidIO aims to combine the best attributes of PCIe and Ethernet. It aims to get the low latency interconnection provided by PCIe and the high scalability achieved with Ethernet. The protocol ensures in order delivery and is implemented in hardware, making it a very efficient solution in terms of energy of CPU usage.

RapidIO is being used in almost all 4G base station cell phone transmitters around the world and was chosen by NASA as the interconnect technology for space travelling devices. It is also widely used as an interconnect technology in embedded systems world.

Although RapidIO main usage currently is embedded systems, it could also be used to interconnect servers in a computing cluster. One of the problems with Big Data Technologies is that it is not possible to store all the data in the same place and the data needed in a given processing operation may not be on the same machine processing it but on other place. The needs for the data to be transferred around the network and the latency of the transfer operation has a direct impact on the time some processing operation takes to conclude. RapidIO is an open interconnect standard aiming to provide very low latency. Reducing the latency in a big data system directly increases the efficiency of the system. Using RapidIO as the interconnect technology in a big data system could provide many advantages if the system correctly uses the features offered by RapidIO.

1.1 Motivation

CERN has a huge IT infrastructure, uses hardware and software from several vendors, and it is necessary to control if everything is working as expected. In order to do that there are systems that collect log data from the several different hardware devices and software products used at CERN. This logging data is collected, aggregated and then stored in a Hadoop repository. Currently the size of this data is around 50 Tb and this data is increasing at an average of 500 Gb per day with peaks of 800Gb.

The Hadoop cluster is interconnected using both 1 Gigabit and 10 Gigabit Ethernet. Due to the rapid increase in data size, it is not possible to perform near real time analytics on the logging data. Real time analytics would be very beneficial to some departments at CERN, for example the computer security.

Given the nature of the experiments being carried on at CERN and given that those experiments rely on the IT infrastructure, a computer security incident could be catastrophic. CERN is a large organization, with many employees and using a big IT infrastructure, both of those two factors increase the risk of a computer incident. In order to mitigate the risks CERN tries to monitor everything that could be related with a problem. Computer security team performs a lot of analysis of the logged data in order to detect and contain security problems. The faster this information could be analysed the faster the problem could be contained. Not being able to do real time analytics on the logging data is a potential security risk.

1.2 Objectives

The objective this work, is to investigate if using RapidIO instead of Ethernet as an interconnect technology in the Hadoop cluster of CERN would provide some benefit to CERN. Like provide near real time analytics making the response to a security threat faster and containing its possible effects.

When using a Hadoop cluster, the information is in most of the times not only stored on a single server, it is replicated in several servers. Information needs to be transmitted from server to server. In order to test this scenario of transmitting large amounts of information from one server to another over a RapidIO a file transfer application using RapidIO as the interconnect technology was created.

The creation of a file transfer application over RapidIO allows to:

- Internally validate the throughput of RapidIO interconnect when used in a real world software application.
- Internally validate the library provided (libmport) that enables software access to the RapidIO interconnect technology.
- Create a real software program that takes advantage of RapidIO multicast. Multicasting is a feature offered by RapidIO and if correctly used can provide great benefits when the same information needs to be transmitted to many receptors. This scenario happens in a Hadoop cluster and a file transfer application allows to test it in a simple way.

Creating a file transfer application was the first objective of a long term project born from a partnership between Integrated Device Technology, Inc. (IDT) and CERN and this document describes the application created.

1.3 Document structure

The main objective of this document is to provide a view of the file transfer application created. This document is structured as follows:

In the next section, is presented an overview of the hardware where this application was deployed and tested and an overview of the library that allows for RapidIO interconnect by the application created.

After the hardware and library overview, follows a description of the file transfer application itself, its architecture, its components and API's they provide together with functionalities offered and a description of how to use the application.

When creating an application the job does not end when the application is done. It is necessary to have some degree of confidence that the application is working correctly. The methodology used to do this is provided in section four.

In the last section of this document the main conclusions taken during this work and the possible future tasks are presented.

2 CLUSTER AND DEVELOPMENT OVERVIEW

2.1 Hardware and OS Description

The hardware used to test and deploy this application is composed of four computers described as follows:

- Asus Z97 Motherboard with Intel i5 4440-3.1GHz processor (4 cores, 6 MB cache)
- 4GB DDR3 Memory
- 500GB SATA hard drive

Each of the computers contains a hardware board that implements the RapidIO protocol, more concretely a RapidExpress Bridge card. All the RapidExpress Bridge cards are directly connected via cable to a RapidExpress Switch Box that switch the RapidIO packets between the machines. The Rapid Express switch boxes contain the IDT CPS-1432 switch chip with 8 ports.

The operation system being run on the 4 machines part of the cluster is Linux Fedora 20 with a customized version of the kernel v3.16.7.

Figure 3 Test cluster

Figure 2 RapidExpress Switch Box

Figure 4 RapidExpress Bridge card

2.2 Development Library Overview

The file transfer application uses the libmport library provided by IDT. This library is built in c programming language and depends two mandatory device drivers:

1. `RIO_MPORT_CDEV` - This is a normal Linux char device driver that can be used with the standard interfaces (read, write, mmap and ioctl). This driver allows the software to programmatically change RapidIO operation parameters. It is also responsible for implementing distributed shared memory between machines. Shared memory will be further described in this document.
2. `RIO_CM` - This driver has identical semantics to an IP socket interface, it is responsible for implementing a channelizing messaging system. The messaging system provided is totally hardware independent.

The libmport library contains a set of functions that allows simplified access to the functionalities provided by this device driver. Although IDT provides high level libraries, the libmport library used is a low-level library providing access to the features of the drivers by normal c function calls, without doing complex side work.

The two main communication paradigms in the RapidIO protocol are channelized messages and a global shared memory between machines offered by `RIO_CM` driver and `RIO_MPORT_CDEV` driver respectively. The file transfer application makes uses of both communication paradigms. In order to provide a better understanding of the application created both of the paradigms will be described in the next subsections.

2.2.1 Channelized Messages

RapidIO channelized messages are very good for short duration operations. The typical good use case for messaging system is signalize transactions. In the file transfer application messages are used to signalize the starting of a file transfer, and to signalize when parts of file are transmitted. The overhead of instantiating a message communication is very low. RapidIO messages can contain up to 4Kb. At maximum size, a RapidIO message is transmitted in 16 RapidIO packets.

2.2.2 Shared Memory

RapidIO shared memory module implements global distributed shared memory system between the devices of a cluster. It has a very large throughput and should be used for large transfers. Recurring to this module it is possible to have large data structures shared among the machines of a cluster. In the file transfer application the contents of the file itself are transferred around machines using blocks of shared memory.

RapidIO shared memory supports multi cast. The same information could be written to shared memory of multiple machines with just a simple operation. Thanks to this functionally the file transfer application created is able to transmit a given file simultaneously to many receivers.

3 SOFTWARE OVERVIEW

In this section an overview of the file transfer application created is presented. The document starts by presenting the architecture of the system. In order to create the application an application layer protocol had to be created after presenting the architecture this protocol is also presented. Then we present the components in which the software is divided and what reusable API's the components offer. This section continues by summarizing the features that the application offers and concludes with an explanation how to use the features offered.

3.1 General Architecture

The application created uses the client-server paradigm. The server is continuously running in background, listening for requests of the client. The requests arrive to the server using RapidIO channelized messages. The request informs the server that a given clients wants to send a file.

When a given server receives a request to receive a file, it creates a new child process handles the file receiving operation while the original process stays listening for more requests.

The client does the following steps:

1. Receives information about the file that should be sent to the server and to which server it should be sent.
2. Establishes a messaging communication channel with the desired server.
3. Transmits the file send request.
4. Waits for the server to answer.
5. Transmits the file and exits.

The same machine can be running a client and a server. A machine could a file as server while transmitting a file to another server as a client. Although there is a functional distinction between a client and a server both of them run the same software. This happens because the file transfer application could be configured to start a server and be waiting for files or to be client and be transmitting a file. In order to have a client and a server on the same machine one just needs to start the file transfer application two times with different configurations.

Figure 5 General architecture summary

3.2 Application Level Protocol

As referred on previous section the file transfer application makes use of two RapidIO communication mechanisms: channelized messages and distributed shared memory. This happens because most of the times, it is not possible to transmit a file in a single block of shared memory. The file may not be able to fit on the memory of a given computer. It is also necessary to signalize between machines when a given content in the shared memory is ready to be stored to the disk.

In order to coordinate the use of both communication mechanisms and to transfer the file with success the protocol described in Figure 6 was used.

Figure 6 Application level protocol description

1. At the start the client sends a `SEND_FILE` message containing the name of the file and the file size. When the server receives this message, it allocates a shared memory window. The size of the window is dynamic. The server allocates the minimum window size that is able to contain the file, if the file is able to fit in a single memory window. In the most common case when the file is not able to fit in a single memory window the server allocates the highest window possible.
2. After finishing the allocation of the memory windows, the server sends a `SEND_FILE_ACK` to the client notifying that the shared memory window is allocated and ready to be used. If this notification did not exist the client could have started writing to the shared memory before the server had completed its allocation, which would damage the file.
3. After receiving the notification from the server that it could start transmitting the file, the clients write the first "chunk" of the file to the shared memory allocated on the server. When the writing operation is finished. The client sends a `BLOCK_ACK` message to the

- server, this messages is necessary to notify the server that the contents on the shared memory are ready to be stored on the disk. Without this notification the server could be writing data to the disk before the all the data was in the shared memory.
4. When the data containing a part of a file is stored on the disk the server sends a `BLOCK_ACK` back to client. This notification is necessary to inform the client that the shared memory window is able to store new data. Without this notification the client could have started writing data to the shared memory window before the previous data was stored.

The steps three and four are repeated until all file contents are sent. The same protocol is used in the multicast version of the program. The server does exactly the same operation without any difference compared to the unicast transmission. The client when writing to the shared memory uses a special multicast destination address. RapidIO provided technologies handle the work of writing to the several machines. For the messages, it is not possible in the current environment to use multicasting. In order to overtake this difficulty the client sends messages in unicast. The same message is sent to the several machines and then the client waits until it receives the answer of all of them. This constraint does not have a significant impact given that messages are very small data transfer operations.

3.3 Components And API Description

The file transfer application follows a modular architecture, each module can be used independently of the others. This allows the functionalities offered by a given module to be used in different applications.

There are three main modules on the file transfer application, used by both the client and the server. The description of the functionalities of each module and the public API's each module provides are described in the next subsections.

3.3.1 Messaging Communicator

The messaging communicator module creates a higher level API to use RapidIO channelized messages. This module uses the functions provided by `libmport` library. The module handles all the allocation and release of resources.

When using messaging module the user needs to instantiate a channelized messaging communication. To do the instantiation it needs to pass some parameters like the machine that it should send messages to or the message channel to use. The instantiation process returns a message communication structure (`msgCom`). Using this structure it is possible to send and receive messages. When the module user does not need to use more messages, only a call to a close function is necessary. The close function frees all the resources used.

This module has two main set of functions. One that communicates with one machine. And a set of "multicast" versions that instantiates message communication with many machine and sends/receives to/from many machines.

The library provided to use RapidIO does not currently support message multicasting. The "multicast" version of the messaging communication system transmits the messages in unicast to the different machines. The "multicast" functions call the unicast ones in cycle.

The functions provided by messaging communicator module and a brief description of what they do is provided as follows.

- **int `initReceiverMsgService`** (int port, int channel, void(*onNewConnection)(riodp_socket_t *, void *arg), void *newConnectionArg)
Function that creates a message server that stays listening for incoming messages. When a new message is received a function called as argument is called.
- **msgCom `connectToMsgService`** (int mport_id, int remote_channel, int remote_destid)
Creates a message communication structure to exchange messages with the desired machine, allocating the necessary resources.
- **int `sendMsgSocket`** (riodp_socket_t socket, void *msg_tx)
Sends the message stored in msg_tx to connection specified in socket.
- **void * `receiveMsgSocket`** (riodp_socket_t socket, void *msg_rx)
Receives a message from the connection specified in socket and stores it in msg_tx.
- **int `closeMsgConnection`** (msgCom *msgCom)
Closes the message connection specified by msgCom.
- **void `endSocketConnection`** (riodp_socket_t *socket, void *msg_rx)
Function that closes a socket connection.
- **msgCom * `connectToMultiplceServices`** (int mport_id, int remote_channel, int remote_destids[], int numberOfNodes)
Creates several message communication structures to exchange messages with the desired machines.
- **void `sendMultipleMsgs`** (msgCom *connections, int numberOfConnections)
Sends a message to multiple machines the message send is always the one store on the message buffer of the first connection.
- **void `receiveMultipleMsgs`** (msgCom *connections, int numberOfConnections)
Function that receives a message from the connections specified in connections.
- **int `closeMultipleConnections`** (msgCom *connections, int numberOfConnections)
Closes all the message connections array.

3.3.2 Shared Memory Manager

Shared memory module manages all the RapidIO shared memory operations. This module is responsible for allocate and release the resources and use them according to the user calls.

The operation of this module is described as follows:

1. A shared memory window is created and the resources are allocated. Shared memory windows can be inbound or outbound. In inbound windows the information is stored in the computer allocating it and other devices can write to it. Outbound windows are used to write to the inbound windows of other devices.
2. If outbound window mode is selected (if writing to shared memory allocated in another device of the cluster) a call to a function that configure the destination is necessary. This call configures unicast or multicast communication depending if transmitting to one or to several devices. If multicast communication is used this function call the necessary libmport functions with right flags to correctly configure the switch to use multicast communication.

3. After the shared memory window allocation and after the destination configuration the user of this module can use read and writes operations to the shared memory. If multicast mode is being used read operations are not possible.
4. When the shared memory communication is not needed anymore the user of the library just needs to call a function that frees the resources and correctly terminates the RapidIO shared memory communication.

The public functions offered by this module with a brief description is provided as follows:

- **dma dmaInit** (uint32_t mport_id, uint64_t tgt_addr, uint32_t dma_size, int kbuf_mode)
Create a dma structure and intilizes the dma communication process.
- void **dmaConfigDestination** (dma *dma, int *destIDs, int nNodes)
Configure the machines to where information should be transmitted if more than one machine multicast communication is instatiated.
- void **allocateInBuffer** (dma *dma)
Allocates an inbound shared memory window allowing other computers to read and write data from there.
- void **allocateOutBuffer** (dma *dma)
Allocates an outbound shared memory window.
- int **dmaWrite** (dma *dma)
Write the information on buffer to the shared window of other machine.
- unsigned int **getWindowSize** (unsigned int desiredSize)
Computes the window size to use. It allocates the minimum window size that is able to contain the desired size. In the most common case when the desired size is not able to fit in a single memory window so the function returns the highest window size possible.
- void **closeInDma** (dma *dma)
Closes and inbound dma shared memory window.
- void **closeOutDma** (dma *dma)
Closes and outbound dma shared memory connection.

3.3.3 File Transfer

The file transfer module is responsible for using the two modules described before to send the file. This module receives the information provided by the user (most of it in the fileTransfer structure). Then it calls the functions provided by other modules to do the file transfer operation.

This module is responsible for implementing the application level protocol described in section 3.2. It is also this module that handles all IO operations from the disk.

This module provides two public main functions described as follows:

- void **sendFile** (int mport_id, int channel, int kbuf_mode, int *destinations, int nNodes, char *filePath)
Sends a file over rapidIO.
- void **startFileReceiver** (int mport_id, int channel, int kbuf_mode)
Starts a file receiving server.

3.4 Functionalities and Use cases

The File Transfer application allows to send files from one machine to another using a command line interface that aims to be simple to use.

The usage information of the main use cases (send and receive a file) will now be presented.

`./filetransfer receiver <port> <channel> <mode>`

Starts a file receiving server.

Parameters:

<i>port</i>	RapidIO port identifier
<i>channel</i>	RapidIO message channel to use, integer > 0
<i>mode</i>	use a kernel buffer if 1, a normal memory buffer if 0

`./filetransfer send <port> <channel> <mode> <filePath> <destinations>`

Sends a file over RapidIO

Parameters:

<i>port</i>	RapidIO port identifier
<i>channel</i>	RapidIO message channel to use, integer > 0
<i>mode</i>	use a kernel buffer if 1, a normal memory buffer if 0
<i>filePath</i>	Path of the file to be sent
<i>destinations</i>	Destination ID's of the machines that will receive the file. One or more.

4 VALIDATION

4.1 Experimental Subjects

In order to test the file transfer application mainly random files with sizes of one and two gigabytes were used. As a control some small files +-250 bytes and a 10Gb file were also used. The random files were generated using the unix command: `dd if=/dev/urandom of=1GB.bin bs=64M count=16`.

4.2 Experimental Setup

After generating the random files the md5sum hash of the file was computed. Then the different files were transferred around the machines. At the end of the transfer md5sum of the file on receiver side was computed and compared with the original one. This allows us to check if the files are being received correctly.

In order to validate the values of the throughput, the code was instrumented to measure the time shared memory operations take to complete. The function used to count the time was `clock_gettime`. The function was invoked before a shared memory operation started and invoked again after it finishes. All the differences were summed together. The value of this sum represents the time spent in network operations over RapidIO shared memory. The size of the file was divided by this time to obtain the throughput.

In order to measure to throughput over RapidIO, a one gigabyte file was sent 50 times using the file transfer application. The throughputs of the shared memory operations of all the executions were collected.

4.3 Experimental Results

The final version of the software was able to transfer all the different test subjects with success (according to the md5 hash comparison).

There results obtained, during the transfer of the 1GB file 50 times are summarized on the following table:

Average throughput	1404 MB/s
Standard deviation	105 MB/s
Minimum	924 MB/s
Maximum	1505 MB/s

An average throughput of 1404 MB/s was observed with a standard deviation of 105 MB/s which allow us to conclude with 95% confidence level that the average throughput of the shared memory operations on the file transfer application is between 1375 MB/s and 1433 MB/s. The maximum possible theoretical throughput over RapidIO on the cluster is 14.5 Gigabits per second. The API

used by our project is not yet totally optimized allowing a maximum of 12 Gigabits per second. This limitation is expected to be solved soon on a future release of the library used.

The results obtained are around 11 Gigabits per second, which is close to the maximum achievable at the moment. The difference could be explained by the amount of time calls take to measure, or by operation system interruptions on the software between two measurements. This results prove that in real world applications, it is possible to achieve throughputs very close to the theoretical maximum of RapidIO.

The same file was transferred in multicast to two different machines and no statistically significant alteration on shared memory throughputs was observed. This allows us to conclude that the use of multicast is ideal when the same information needs to be transferred to many machines around a cluster.

The reported throughputs only take into account the RapidIO shared memory transfer time, not the total time the file took to be transferred. If the total time was taken in consideration the throughput would be limited by IO operations on the hard drive whose speed is very low when compared with the RapidIO throughput.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The creation of a file transfer application allows to validate that RapidIO can be used in a cluster scenario. The main objective of work, create a file transfer application, was accomplished. It was developed and tested with success for the use cases it provides.

The file transfer application allows any file to be transmitted around the cluster in an efficient way where the guarantees needed to transfer a file mainly ensuring correct data deliver and ensuring in order delivery of data are provided by hardware. This is energy efficient and allows the CPU of the servers in a cluster to be dedicated to its main processing tasks without spending cycles implementing a software protocol.

The authors of the application had no previous knowledge about RapidIO, with just a short training they were able to use the libmport library to create a real world application that uses RapidIO interconnect technology. This fact allows to conclude that the learning curve to use RapidIO library is acceptable.

The library provided to use RapidIO interconnect follows some well know communication patterns making it possible to use in different communication scenarios. The library provided is low-level and forces the users of the library to keep track/manage many resources/parameters. This fact makes the library not easy to use in big software applications, it suggests the need of a high level version of the library. The higher level version of the library can manage the resources/parameters and make calls to the existing library. Similarly to what was done with the modules part of this project. There exist high level library's to use RapidIO interconnect that provide structures equivalent to a socket, but the use of this library's was not in the scope of this project.

The results measured allow us to conclude that RapidIO 12 Gbps throughputs can be achieved using a real world applications. The real transfer time of a file is seriously impacted by the velocity of the hard drive. In order for software applications take the maximum of RapidIO they should be designed taking into account RapidIO communication mechanisms. IO operations should be made while other contents are being transmitted over RapidIO. If that is done, RapidIO networking time may have almost zero impact on the time some application needs to complete some task.

5.1 Future Work

As referred when creating an application using RapidIO interconnect the IO operations should be made in parallel with RapidIO transfers. When creating the file transfer application one of the objectives was to make it as simple to understand as possible by creating simple code that makes understanding basic RapidIO usage in software applications easy. Increasing the performance of the file transfer time parallelizing the network operations is the main improvement on the file transfer application that could be made.

Currently is possible on the same computer to be transmitting a file as a client and receiving one as a server at the same time. But it is not possible for a given computer to receive many files from multiple sources at the same time. When a server is occupied receiving a file, if another clients wants to transmit a file, that client needs to wait for the operation currently running on the server to finish. There is a limitation on the number of shared memory windows that can be allocated on RapidIO. If the server is already using a shared memory window but some other is not being used it could inform the client to use the address that is free. In order to use multicasting all the computers need to use a protocol to check which RapidIO addresses are free in all the computers. This involves some effort, but would be a good addition to the file transfer application.

The file transfer application created is part of a project to evaluate RapidIO usage in a big data system at CERN. With the creation of it, it was demonstrated that it is possible to use RapidIO interconnect to move data around a computing cluster both in multicast and in unicast. The next step of the project is initially deploy a Hadoop cluster that supports RapidIO interconnect on the computers used to test this file transfer application and later deploy an Hadoop cluster interconnected with RapidIO with exactly the same hardware and software configuration as the one used normally at CERN.